

PREDICTION OF DELAMINATION AT TERMINATING PLYS IN LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A change in the thickness of an advanced composite laminate due to terminating internal plies acts as a stress riser. A fracture-mechanics based analysis is used to predict the onset of delamination at the terminating ply tip. This analysis consisted of an energy based model and a finite element analysis based on the crack tip stress intensity method. An experimental program was also conducted in order to verify the results of the analytical study. The finding of the analysis was that the presence of terminating plies in a laminate will significantly reduce the load carrying capabilities of the laminate. Good correlation was obtained between the analytical modeling and the test results, indicating that the analytical model may be a useful design aid.

Keywords : Terminating Plies, Fracture, Delamination, Finite Element, Compression.

1. INTRODUCTION

The superior specific strength and stiffness coupled with the ability to selectively reinforce critical load paths have made composite materials ideal for weight critical structures. A summary of the advantages and disadvantages of advanced composite materials is beyond the scope of this paper, however the interested reader is referred to [1] for such a discussion.

In order to make efficient structural configurations utilising advanced composites, the thickness of the structure is often tapered as the requirements to carry load decrease. This is accomplished by terminating or "dropping-off" individual plies. The terminating ply acts as a discontinuity which becomes a stress riser. This type of stress increase can lead to delamination.

Relatively little work has been done in the field of terminating plies, and most has been design specific [2]. More recently, however, fundamental studies of terminating plies in laminates have been undertaken. Analytical work [3] has indicated that stress concentrations do arise in the vicinity of a terminating ply and that interlamina stresses, which can cause delamination, also occur. Experimental work involving both compressive [4] and tensile [5] loading has also been accomplished. It was found that terminating plies had no effect on the load carrying capability in tension, however reduced the compressive load carrying capability considerably. The aim of this study was to determine the effect terminating plies had on the compressive strength of a laminate. In a study conducted by Trethewey [6] it was identified that the failure mode in a laminate with a terminating ply loaded in compression was delamination. The study presented here concentrates on determining the load required to cause delamination growth at the tip of a terminating ply.

2. TERMINATING PLIES

2.1. Terminating Ply Geometry

A laminated fibre composite material is made up of a number of plies which are often terminated at points in a structure. The other layers of the composite are then forced to mould or "flow" around the terminating plies. The effect of such terminating plies on the geometry of a laminate has been studied by Chan and Ochoa [7]. Figure 1, below, from Chan and Ochoa [7] shows the flow of plies around a terminating ply.

Figure 1 : Flow of plies around a terminating ply [7].

Due to the flow of plies around a terminating ply, a void is produced in front of the terminating plies. During the cure process this void becomes filled with the epoxy resin of the matrix. Throughout this paper the epoxy resin filled void at the tip of the terminating plies will be termed the resin pocket. The section of the laminate with the terminating plies will be termed the thick section and the section of the laminate without the terminating plies will be termed the thin section. The region between the thick section and the thin section will be termed the transition region.

2.2. Expected Failure Modes

It was identified by Tretheway [6] and initial testing that the failure mode obtained in compressively loaded laminates with terminating plies was delamination. It was also found that the delamination would always initiate at the tip of the terminating plies and propagate in one of two directions.

Figure 2 : Terminating ply delamination propagation modes.

Figure 2 shows the position of delamination growth in the thick and thin sections respectively. The aim of the analysis was to determine the applied compressive load at which delamination growth occurs in either the thick or thin sections of the laminate.

3. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Delamination has been identified as the expected failure mode in a laminate with a terminating ply. For this reason the analysis concentrated on predicting the compressive load that causes delamination growth. The most successful methods used to predict delamination onset and growth in laminated composites have been fracture-mechanics based techniques. In particular, the branch of fracture mechanics known as linear elastic fracture mechanics. Linear elastic fracture mechanics is based on two assumptions; the first is that the crack tip plastic zone remains relatively small with respect to the crack length and the second is that the growth of the crack remains co-linear. Both these assumptions are satisfied adequately by laminated advanced fibre composites. The plastic zone is constrained to be relatively small by the very closely spaced, highly elastic fibres and the crack growth is generally co-linear, as initial defects within the resin rich interlaminar plane are constrained to grow along that plane by the elastic fibres above and below.

Two models were produced, both of which used linear elastic fracture mechanics to predict the onset and growth of delamination. These two models were a finite element and an analytical model. Both the models use different linear elastic fracture mechanics methods. The two methods used were the stress intensity factor method and the strain energy release rate method.

For the stress intensity factor method the elastic crack tip stress field is written as

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{K}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} f_{ij}(\theta) \tag{1}$$

where

$$K = \sigma\sqrt{\pi a}$$

The factor K in Equation 1 is defined as the stress intensity factor. When the stress intensity factor reaches a critical value, crack extension will occur. The unique stress intensity that causes failure is called the critical stress intensity factor K_C . In the stress intensity approach to fracture, K_C is a measure of the crack growth resistance and has been shown to be a characteristic of a given material.

The other fracture mechanics method used was the strain energy release rate formulation. In this method it is assumed that as a cracked plate is loaded, the work performed is stored as elastic strain energy. When the crack propagates the strain energy is released. Griffith [8] stated "Crack growth can occur if the energy required to form an additional crack of length da can be delivered to the system". The strain energy release rate or crack driving force, G , is defined as,

$$G = \frac{d}{da}(F - U) \tag{2}$$

where F is the work supplied by the movement of external forces and U is the elastic strain energy stored in the body. As with the stress intensity factor method, when the strain energy release rate reaches a critical value, G_C , crack growth occurs. G_C has been shown to be a characteristic of a given material.

3.1. Finite Element Model

The MSC/NASTRAN FE package was chosen for this analysis. One reason for choosing this package was that it has a "crack-tip element" option, enabling stress intensity factors to be obtained directly from the model. In order to determine the load required to cause delamination, a

crack-tip element is used at the point where fracture is expected. This will give stress intensity factors at that point. The loading on the model can then be increased up to a point where the stress intensity factors reach a critical value, K_C . Using this method the load at which delamination will occur can be determined. A 3-dimensional (3D) finite element model was produced using 8 noded isoparametric 3D brick elements. In order to define the material properties of the laminate the properties for a single unidirectional ply were defined using an anisotropic material stiffness matrix. This matrix was then transformed through various angles to give the material properties of the off-axis fibres. The resin pocket at the tip of the terminating plies was given the properties of neat resin. A diagram of the finite element model is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3 : Finite element model geometry.

The crack tip elements were placed in the thick and thin sections of the model. The crack tip elements in the thin section were placed between the plies that flow around the terminating plies, in front of the terminating ply tip. The thick section crack tip elements were placed at the interface between the terminating plies and the surrounding plies of the laminate, as shown in Figure 3. One problem with this modelling technique is that stress intensity factors are obtained as the result. However, the strain energy release rate method has been used more frequently to characterise delamination in laminated composites. Therefore, to make the results compatible with other studies and the analytical model, the stress intensity factors were converted to strain energy release rates using an equation set developed by Paris and Sih [9]. These equations are presented in Equation 3. The S_{ij} terms in Equation 3 are the terms of the extensional stiffness matrix in the laminate constitutive relationship.

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_i &= C_i K_i^2 \\
 C_I &= \left(\frac{S_{11} S_{22}}{2} \right)^{1/2} \left[\frac{S_{22} + 2S_{12} + S_{66}}{S_{11}} + \frac{2S_{11}}{2S_{11}} \right]^{1/2} \\
 C_{II} &= \frac{S_{11}}{2} \left[\frac{S_{22} + 2S_{12} + S_{66}}{S_{11}} + \frac{2S_{11}}{2S_{11}} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The *I* and *II* suffixes in the above equations refer to mode I (the opening mode) and mode II (the sliding or "shear" mode) of fracture respectively. The results of the finite element model are presented in Figures 4 and 5 below. The stress intensity factor results in figure 4 were obtained directly from the model. The strain energy release rate results in figure 5 were calculated from the stress intensity factor results using Equation 3. The results given in Figures 4 and 5 were for the laminate layup $[0/\pm 45/0]_5$ with two terminating 0° plies.

Figure 4 : Stress Intensity factors obtained from the Finite Element model.
 (a) Thin section crack tip element, (b) Thick section crack tip element

Figure 5 : Strain energy release rates, calculated from the stress intensity factors.
 (a) Thin section crack tip element, (b) Thick section crack tip element

It can be noted from these results that the thick section crack tip element experiences mixed-mode loading (I and II), however the loading on the thin section crack tip element is single mode (mode I). The loading on the thick section crack tip element is much higher than that in the thin section, indicating that delamination will grow in the thick section of the laminate prior to delamination growth in the thin section. Finite element models were produced with 1, 2 and 3 terminating plies. The results from varying the number of terminating plies showed that the relative contributions of the mode I and II stress intensity factors in the thick section varied as the number of terminating plies was varied.

3.2. Analytical Model

An analytical model was developed using an analysis based on the strain energy release rate method. In this model the stiffness difference between the thick and thin sections of the laminate was considered. A diagram of the geometry considered in the model is shown in Figure 6. The laminate was basically broken into 3 parts; these being the thick section, the thin section and the transition region. The modulus and area of the thin section is termed E_1A_1 and the thick section is E_2A_2 . The transition region was given the same properties as the thin section. The initial crack length is shown as the length *a* in Figure 6. The amount of strain energy contained in the laminate due to deflection of the specimen caused by applying a compressive load was considered. From this

analysis a relationship relating the strain energy release rate to the applied compressive load was developed. This relationship is given in Equation 4.

Figure 6 : Geometry considered in analytical model

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2w^2} \left\{ \frac{1}{E_{thin}t_{thin}} - \frac{1}{E_{thick}t_{thick}} \right\} \quad (4)$$

In Equation 4, E is Young's modulus, t is the specimen thickness, w is the specimen width, P is the applied loading and G is the strain energy release rate in the specimen. In order to determine the onset of delamination the following failure analysis was applied.

$$\left\{ \frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}} \right\}^m + \left\{ \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}} \right\}^n = 1 \quad (5)$$

When Equation 5 is satisfied crack growth or delamination will occur. To apply the failure criteria given in Equation 5, the strain energy release rate obtained using equation 4 must be broken down into its separate G_I and G_{II} components. To break down the total strain energy release rate, G , the results of the finite element model were used. The total strain energy release rate was broken down using the following relationship,

$$G_I = \frac{RG_{TOTAL}}{(1+R)} \quad \text{where,} \quad R = \frac{G_I}{G_{II}} \quad (6)$$

The relationship R was determined from the results of the finite element model for the thick section crack tip element. The finite element model showed that the ratio, R , varied as the number of terminating plies was varied. To assess the effect of a varying value of R , an equation was developed from the results of the finite element model which relates the amount of mode I strain energy release rate to the total strain energy release rate, ie.

$$\frac{G_I}{G_{TOTAL}} = \frac{R}{(1+R)} = 0.804 - 0.656 \cdot \left(\frac{t_{thin}}{t_{thick}} \right) \quad (7)$$

Using Equation 7 the effect of a variable ratio could be assessed. Many laminate configurations were analysed, however in every configuration the laminate was kept symmetrical so the effect of bending extension coupling would be removed. The values of m and n in Equation 5 were also varied however $m = n = 1$ was found to give results which compared most favourably with the test data. The results of the analytical model using variable and fixed R ratios is given in Figure 7.

Figure 7 : Results of analytical model; (a) Constant R ratio, (b) Variable and constant R ratio.

The results of the analytical model show that as the number of terminating plies is increased, the strength of the laminate decreases (or the load that causes delamination growth is lower). It is also noticed that varying the R ratio as predicted by the finite element model has the effect of making the failure curve steeper. The layout analysed in the above example was a 32 ply quasi-isotropic base laminate with the number of terminating plies varied as indicated. These results are presented for comparison with the test data.

4. TEST PROGRAM

Along with the analytical models a test program was performed. The test program consisted of compression testing laminates with terminating plies. One of the major problems to overcome with this type of test was that of specimen buckling. Long, slender specimens were used (250mm long, 25mm wide and up to 4 mm thick), so significant delamination growth could be observed. The thickness of the laminate varied due to the inclusion of the terminating plies, and the available compression rigs could not cater for variable thickness specimens. For this reason, a special rig was developed which could be adjusted to cater for specimens of variable thickness. The rig had descreet bars along the gauge length of the specimen which could be adjusted along the length of the specimen. Care was also taken to produce specimens which were as close to symmetric as possible.

The specimens were loaded by displacement in a servo-hydraulic testing machine. The results presented in Figure 8 are for the load to cause delamination growth.

Figure 8 : Comparison of test and analytical data.

The results in Figure 8 indicate that good correlation was obtained between the test data and the analytical model. The analytical results presented in Figure 8 are for a constant R ratio. The laminates used for the results in Figure 8 were 32 ply quasi-isotropic base laminates with 0° terminating plies. In all the specimens delamination initiated at the thick section of the laminate in the position indicated by the finite element model. Further loading would cause the delamination to

propagate away from the terminating ply tip. In most of the test specimens secondary delamination would occur in the thin section of the laminate at the tip of the terminating plies, where the surrounding plies meet. The delamination would then propagate away from the terminating ply tip.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this research study was to determine a method of predicting the strength reduction in a laminate due to the inclusion of terminating plies. It was also required that the method used to determine the strength reduction be simple enough to apply by a design engineer as a quick check of the laminate strength. The results of the analytical model compared well with the test data. This would indicate that the analytical model is an adequate method of determining the strength reduction due to the inclusion of terminating plies in a laminate, without the use of a more detailed analysis such as a finite element model.

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